

Tool 17

Inclusiveness checklist

Welcome to the Citizen Science Starter Kit.

This template is part of Module 4 “Getting started with citizen science” (phase 2 – develop) and helps you to set up inclusive citizen science. The template¹ is a checklist with good practices to reach underrepresented groups, or vulnerable and marginalized communities.

Please download this template to your own folder and fill it in on your local computer. If you have any further questions about this template, please contact citizenscience@vub.be.

PARTICIPATORY RESEARCH	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define your target groups and understand their reality (For instance: what type of motivations or barriers could there be to their participation, e.g. in terms of time availability, physical health, (digital) literacy, etc. Focus groups with the target groups or interviews with experts can help to define these elements) 	●
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Set up the research in a collaborative way (For instance: understand how the data collected connects to the local community, and frame the problem as a local issue to help citizens feel connected to the stakes of your project) 	●
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply different levels of engagement with multiple moments to contribute to the project (For instance: do not only involve citizen scientists in the collection of the data, but also in the analysis, co-creation of methods, and formulation of conclusions, and, within these activities, provide different means of participation, or levels of difficulty) 	●

¹ This template is developed based on insights gathered from : 1) Veeckman, C., Talboom, S., Gijssels, L., Devoghel, H., Duerinckx, A. (2019). Communication in Citizen Science. A practical guide to communication and engagement in citizen science. SCIVIL, Leuven, Belgium. 2) Varga, D., Doran, C., Ortega, B. and Segú Odriozola, M., 2023. How can Inclusive Citizen Science Transform the Sustainable Development Agenda? Recommendations for a Wider and More Meaningful Inclusion in the Design of Citizen Science Initiatives. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 8(1), p.29.DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.572> 3) the SOCIO-BEE inclusion and non-discrimination checklist developed by Maria Lopez Belloso, Mabel Segú Odriozola and Usue Beloki Marañón from DEUSTO University (forthcoming in 2023) and 4) Insights from the [Urban ReLeaf](#) Inclusiveness communication policy and strategies

CITIZEN SCIENCE TOOLS	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure accessibility to the citizen science tools. The citizen science tools should be designed in such a way that everyone can use them to the greatest extent possible (For instance: the tools are adapted for people with a range of disabilities) • The citizen science tools should be simple and intuitive to use (For instance: everyone is able to use the tools regardless of the participant's experience, knowledge, language, ...) • Digital literacy skills of the target groups are taken into account (For instance: citizen scientists have access and the necessary skills to attend an online webinar) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • •
RECRUITMENT	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Search for relevant intermediaries (For instance: contact socio-cultural institutions or welfare organisations, poverty associations, youth organisations, community centres, ...) • Search for local, informal organisations and individuals (For instance: community workers, students in a diversity internship programme, buddies/volunteers for helping refugees, ...) • In consultation with the target groups, choose the appropriate communication channels and tactics (For instance: digital or non-digital communication, usage of the tactics or tools of the intermediary organisation, ...) • Appoint trusted spokespersons for recruitment and communication (For instance: provide trained moderators or facilitators in fostering inclusive participation, provide individualized support, ...) • Define the level of vulnerability of your target groups in order to have a clear understanding of their profile (For instance: is it social vulnerability, economic, or cognitive vulnerability?) • Ensure a gender balance (For instance: apply gender quotas to increase the number of women, support gender-balanced representation in communications) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • • • •

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide a proper incentive for the target groups (For instance: tickets for public transport, a meal (voucher), ...) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •
COMMUNICATION	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply inclusive language practices (For instance: gender-inclusive language, age-inclusive language, people-first language, self-identification, ...) • Avoid stigmatization or labelling of persons into a category of vulnerability (For instance: people may not describe themselves as vulnerable, although they could be categorized as such under certain definitions) • Translate the communication in other languages or provide a translator at public events (For instance: Dutch, English and mother language of the target group) • Perform a simple and clear language check (For instance: is the information comprehensible for your target group? Did you take the reading level of your target group into account? Are you avoiding academic jargon?) • Develop a clear lay-out and design (For instance: a clear lay-out aids your target audience in understanding the information more quickly, making use of lists, enough white space, subtitles, considering colour blindness, ...) • Use realistic and authentic images (For instance: avoid touristic photographs of your cities and use authentic images, avoid stereotypes, ...) • Publish an inclusiveness communication policy (For instance: raise awareness among all your project stakeholders about inclusive communication practices and the ethical principles that you wish to apply, have a mechanism in place for reporting inappropriate conduct, ...) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • • • • •
TIME AND PLACE	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organise meetings at a place and time that is convenient for your target group (For instance: the venue of the intermediary organisation, outside working hours, ...) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide secure places (For instance: creating welcoming, respectful and safe environments, both physical and virtual) • The venue is easily accessible for the designated target groups (For instance: elevator access, clear legible signs, ...) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • •
EVALUATION	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish some inclusion criteria at the start of the project (For instance: defining some KPIs based on gender and social class) • Monitor the participants' demographics (For instance: perform an analysis on available statistics (open data), or through participative investigation of the context throughout the project to implement mitigating actions if necessary) • Understand the barriers to participation (For instance: explore the different barriers to participation among the target groups and design the activities accordingly) • Evaluate how inclusive your project and research team is (For instance: an equal balance between males and females, a more diverse team in terms of ethnicity,) • Disaggregate data to share outcomes of different groups (For instance: split up the analysis by income, age, disability, or other characteristics) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • • •